

Active Nail Fold Video Capillaroscopy Scleroderma Pattern in A Patient with Gastric Antral Vascular Ectasia (GAVE) Syndrome

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Citation: Sehreen Mumtaz, Florentina Berianu. Active Nail Fold Video Capillaroscopy Scleroderma Pattern in A Patient with Gastric Antral Vascular Ectasia (GAVE) Syndrome. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*. 2024;3(5):1-2

Received Date: 22 May, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 30 May, 2024; **Published Date:** 02 June, 2024

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PRESENTATION

68-year-old Caucasian female initially presented with fatigue and acute symptomatic iron deficiency anemia with hemoglobin of 7.2 g/dL with a history of recurrent gastrointestinal bleeding. Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) showed Gastric Antral Vascular Ectasia (GAVE) and a duodenal AVM. Within 6 months she developed major weight loss, progressive dysphagia, and dyspnea on exertion. She was seen in rheumatology clinic for abnormal Antinuclear Antibodies (ANA) at 1:320 and elevated Ribonucleoprotein antibody (RNP) 7.3 U. Pulmonary function tests revealed moderate diffusing capacity of the lungs for carbon monoxide (DLCO) reduction. A Nailfold Videocapillaroscopy (NVC) was performed for evaluation for underlying connective tissue disease.

A.

B.

A. Nailfold videocapillaroscopy exhibiting a giant capillary loop (54.7 micrometer in apical diameter, specific parameter for diagnosis of systemic sclerosis >50 micrometers, magnification 200x (1). Evidence of

superficial edema which is hyperrefractive and enlarged capillaries.

B. Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) displayed severe gastric antral vascular ectasia without bleeding in the gastric antrum and was treated with argon plasma coagulation (APC).

DISCUSSION

The result of the NVC was consistent with active scleroderma pattern. In a patient with Raynaud phenomenon, positive ANA and the presence of even a single giant capillary, reduced number of capillaries and microhaemorrhages on nailfold videocapillaroscopy (NVC) is a validated criterion for the diagnosis of systemic sclerosis [1]. Rapid progression of symptoms with multi organ involvement prompted ongoing evaluation for bone marrow transplant. A randomized clinical trial noted 22.3% incidence of GAVE in systemic sclerosis patients [2]. A high index of suspicion is crucial for identification of connective tissue disease in patients with GAVE. Our case uniquely describes GAVE as the initial manifestation related to systemic sclerosis, confirmed by NVC with the presence of an active scleroderma pattern. Our patient was also RNP antibody positive which has been projected to be linked to early development of GAVE in systemic sclerosis patients [3].

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